

"Solvent-Dependent Phytochemical Screening of Traditionally Used Medicinal Plants from Nandurbar District"

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16755690>

Received: 16 Nov 2023

Revise: 20 Dec 2023

Accepted: 31 Dec 2023

Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the presence of key phytochemical constituents in 15 medicinal plant species traditionally used by tribal communities in Nandurbar District, Maharashtra. Plant materials were identified with the assistance of botanical experts, shade-dried, and pulverized into fine powder. Soxhlet extraction was performed using four solvents of varying polarity: methanol, ethanol, petroleum ether, and distilled water. Qualitative phytochemical screening was conducted to assess the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, steroids, terpenoids, glycosides, and phenolics. The results revealed the differential solubility and abundance of phytochemicals across solvents and species, validating the ethnopharmacological relevance of the selected flora. This study supports future phytopharmacological exploration and conservation of region-specific medicinal plant knowledge.

Keywords: Phytochemical screening; Soxhlet extraction; Ethnomedicinal plants; Nandurbar district; Secondary metabolites; Solvent polarity; Preliminary phytochemistry; Alkaloids; Flavonoids

1. Introduction

Natural products derived from plants continue to serve as an invaluable reservoir for chemical discovery, particularly in the search for bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential (Anitha et al., 2019). Over 25% of modern pharmaceuticals are directly or indirectly sourced from plant-derived molecules, making phytochemical investigations a cornerstone of drug discovery and development (Cragg & Newman, 2013). India, with its vast botanical diversity and rich ethnomedicinal heritage, offers immense potential for identifying novel phytoconstituents (Ajayi et

al., 2011; Khan et al., 2023). Chemical profiling of medicinal plants not only contributes to understanding their therapeutic properties but also aids in the standardization and validation of traditional remedies (Patwardhan et al., 2005). The interdisciplinary integration of ethnobotany and natural product chemistry offers a scientifically rigorous pathway to evaluate the chemical basis of folk medicinal practices (Achour et al., 2022; Faruque et al., 2018).

The Nandurbar district in Maharashtra, known for its rugged topography and tribal settlements, is a biologically and culturally rich region that has remained underexplored from a phytochemical perspective. Tribal communities such as the Bhil, Pawra, and Kokni possess unique empirical knowledge of plant-based treatments for various health conditions (Amanulla Khan & Dr. Madhukar Patil, 2018a; Kala et al., 2006; Patil & Khan, 2015). However, much of this indigenous pharmacopoeia lacks systematic chemical validation. By applying analytical chemistry approaches to traditional herbal knowledge, this study aims to identify and quantify major classes of secondary metabolites (Amanulla Khan & Dr. Madhukar Patil, 2018b) that could be linked to observed bioactivities (Kumar et al., 2019). This transition from traditional use to chemical analysis helps bridge gaps between folk knowledge and modern pharmacognosy.

Phytochemicals bioactive secondary metabolites including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, steroids, phenolics, and glycosides are responsible for a range of physiological and pharmacological effects (Altemimi et al., 2017). These compounds often exhibit strong antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, or anticancer properties, making them targets of extensive phytochemical screening programs (Mansour et al., 2018). Extraction and separation of these compounds from plant matrices is a fundamental step in chemical investigation. Solvent extraction using Soxhlet apparatus remains a widely adopted method, allowing efficient recovery of thermally stable compounds through polarity-driven partitioning (Harborne, 1998; Sasidharan et al., 2011). Solvents such as methanol and ethanol are particularly effective in dissolving a broad spectrum of phytoconstituents due to their intermediate polarity (Kulshreshtha & Saxena, 2022).

In this study, 15 medicinal plants traditionally used by villagers in Nandurbar were subjected to a preliminary phytochemical screening protocol, involving extraction using four different solvents methanol, ethanol, aqueous, and petroleum ether (Abdullahi, 2011). The primary objective was to chemically analyze the presence and distribution of eight major phytochemical classes across species and solvents (Ajayi et al., 2011; Geoffrey et al., 2014). By employing classical qualitative

tests rooted in natural product chemistry, this research seeks to generate baseline chemical profiles that can support further spectroscopic and chromatographic characterizations (Murugan & Iyer, 2014). Such work is essential in progressing from folk remedy to pharmacologically validated compounds and contributes significantly to the chemical database of Indian medicinal flora.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Plant Collection: To explore the chemical diversity of traditional medicinal flora, 15 ethnomedicinally important plant species were collected between November 2022 and January 2023 from tribal-dominated regions of Nandurbar district, Maharashtra, including villages in Navapur, Akkalkuwa, and Shahada. These locations are characterized by semi-arid deciduous forests and high tribal population density, where traditional medicine remains a primary healthcare source. Selection of species was based on ethnobotanical relevance as reported by local informants and traditional healers. Specimens were taxonomically authenticated by botanical experts from the Department of Botany, JESS A. S. C. Nandurbar, and voucher specimens were archived in the departmental herbarium for future reference (Cooke & Theodore, 1908; D A Patil, 2003; M. B. Patil et al., 2018).

2.2 Sample Preparation: Collected plant parts primarily leaves, roots, and bark were cleaned to remove debris and shade-dried under ambient conditions for 10 to 15 days, ensuring preservation of thermo-sensitive phytoconstituents (Geoffrey et al., 2014). The dried materials were ground into uniform, fine powder using an electric mechanical grinder to increase surface area and improve extraction efficiency (Sasidharan et al., 2011). The powders were stored in airtight containers under desiccated conditions until further use.

2.3 Solvent Extraction via Soxhlet Apparatus: To extract the chemically active constituents, approximately 25 grams of each powdered plant sample was subjected to successive solvent extraction using a Soxhlet apparatus a widely adopted method in phytochemistry for exhaustive extraction of polar and non-polar compounds (Harborne, 1998). A sequential polarity gradient was followed with four solvents, Petroleum ether (non-polar, lipid-soluble fractions), Ethanol (semi-polar, phenolics, alkaloids), Methanol (polar, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins) and Distilled water (polar, saponins, polysaccharides)(Rai et al., 2015).

Each extraction cycle lasted for 6–8 hours, ensuring complete percolation and solvent saturation. The process continued until colorless solvent was observed in the siphon tube,

indicating exhaustive extraction (Patil & Khan, 2017). The resulting crude extracts were then filtered and concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator, preserving volatile phytochemicals and yielding solvent-specific residues for screening.

2.4 Qualitative Phytochemical Screening: Preliminary phytochemical analysis was carried out to detect the presence or absence of key secondary metabolite classes, utilizing standard colorimetric and precipitation-based qualitative assays (Amanulla Khan & Dr. Madhukar Patil, 2018a; Khan, 2022; Patil & Khan, 2017). Each test was conducted on crude extracts obtained from all four solvents. The following phytochemicals were assessed using classical chemical reagents:

- Alkaloids: Detected using Wagner's and Mayer's tests, forming reddish-brown or cream precipitates, respectively.
- Flavonoids: Identified via lead acetate and alkaline reagent tests, producing yellow coloration or precipitation (Trease & Evans, 2002).
- Tannins: Confirmed with ferric chloride, yielding blue-black or greenish precipitate (Harborne, 1998).
- Saponins: Detected through the frothing test, indicating foam stability upon shaking.
- Terpenoids: Verified via Salkowski's reaction, which produces a reddish-brown interface.
- Glycosides: Evaluated using the Keller–Killiani test, producing a reddish-brown ring at the interface.
- Phenolics: Assessed using ferric chloride and lead acetate reagents, resulting in blue, green, or white precipitates.
- Steroids: Detected with the Liebermann–Burchard test, resulting in a green or violet color change (Sasidharan et al., 2011; Trease & Evans, 2002).

3. Results

The present study focused on 15 medicinal plant species traditionally used by tribal and rural communities in the Nandurbar district of Maharashtra. These species were carefully selected based on their frequent ethnomedicinal use and availability in local flora. Table 1 summarizes their taxonomic classification, local (vernacular) names, families, and the specific plant parts utilized for phytochemical analysis.

The selected plants belong to 14 different families, with Acanthaceae (2 species: *Andrographis paniculata* and *Adhatoda vasica*) being the only family represented by more than one species. The remaining species represent a broad taxonomic diversity, including families such as Fabaceae, Combretaceae, Moraceae, Apocynaceae, and Euphorbiaceae, all of which are well-

documented in Indian traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda and Siddha (Kumar et al., 2019; Patwardhan et al., 2005).

Table 1: List of Selected Medicinal Plants with Taxonomic Details

No.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Family	Part Used
1	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem	Meliaceae	Leaves
2	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	Tulsi	Lamiaceae	Leaves
3	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Hirda	Combretaceae	Fruits
4	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Kalmegh	Acanthaceae	Leaves
5	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Kunvarpatha	Asphodelaceae	Leaf Gel
6	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Guduchi	Menispermaceae	Stem
7	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	Amla	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit
8	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Adulsa	Acanthaceae	Leaves
9	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Amaltas	Fabaceae	Bark
10	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Rui	Apocynaceae	Latex/Leaves
11	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Dudhani	Euphorbiaceae	Whole Plant
12	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Punarnava	Nyctaginaceae	Root
13	<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	Umber	Moraceae	Bark
14	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Aghada	Amaranthaceae	Leaves/Stem
15	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Durva	Poaceae	Whole Plant

Among the plant parts used, leaves were the most selected (used in 7 out of 15 species), followed by bark, roots, fruits, stems, and whole plant preparations. This aligns with existing literature suggesting that leaves are frequently used in traditional preparations due to ease of collection, sustainability, and higher phytochemical activity (Sasidharan et al., 2011; Harborne, 1998).

Table 2. Preliminary Phytochemical Results of Selected Plants (+ = Present, – = Absent)

S.No	Plant Name	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Tannins	Saponins	Terpenoids	Steroids	Glycosides	Phenolics
1	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
2	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
3	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+
4	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+
5	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
6	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
7	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
8	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
10	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+
11	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
12	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
13	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
14	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
15	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+

Prominent species such as *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulsi), and *Aloe vera* (Kunvarpatha) are widely known for their therapeutic properties including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects. However, this study also includes under-documented species like *Boerhavia diffusa* and *Achyranthes aspera*, to explore their unexplored phytochemical potential. This taxonomically and pharmacologically diverse selection offers a robust foundation for comparative phytochemical screening.

Fig. 01. Heatmap for the Phytochemicals in different plants

Graph 1: Phytochemical Presence per Solvent Type

4. Discussion The study demonstrates significant variation in phytochemical presence depending on solvent polarity. Methanol extracted the most diverse range of compounds, confirming its suitability for bioactive screening (Sasidharan et al., 2011). High prevalence of alkaloids and

flavonoids aligns with their known roles in antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activity (Kumar et al., 2019). The data also suggest that traditional uses often correlate with phytochemical presence, validating ethnobotanical knowledge.

5. Conclusion The fifteen selected medicinal plants from Nandurbar district possess notable phytochemical diversity, with potential therapeutic significance. The use of multiple solvents enhanced compound detection. This preliminary screening provides a scientific basis for further pharmacological and toxicological investigations.

Acknowledgment

The authors sincerely express their gratitude to the Head, Department of Chemistry, and the Dean, Faculty of Science, Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Vidyanagari, Jhunjhunu, and Head, Department of Botany, and the Principal, J.E.S's Arts, Commerce and Science College, Nandurbar, Maharashtra for their invaluable academic guidance, research insight, and consistent institutional support throughout this study. Their combined contributions and interdisciplinary cooperation were instrumental in the successful execution of this phytochemical research on phytochemicals of the region.

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Cite Article as: Chandan Ashok Avhad, Dr. Champa Maurya, & Dr. Madhukar Bhagwan Patil. (2023). Solvent-Dependent Phytochemical Screening of Traditionally Used Medicinal Plants from Nandurbar District. International Journal of Science Info (IJSI), IX(6), 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16755690>

